

A Critical Study on Business Strategies of Cognizant Ltd.

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Abstract

Cognizant is a multinational corporation that provides IT services, including digital, Technology, Consulting, And operations services. It is headquartered in Teaneck, New Jersey, United States. It was founded as an in-house technology unit of Dun & Bradstreet in 1994, And started serving external clients in 1996. Cognizant provides information technology, Information security, and Consulting, ITO and BPO services. These include business & technology consulting, Systems integration, Application development & maintenance, IT infrastructure services, Analytics, Business Intelligence, Data warehousing, Customer relationship management, Supply chain management, Engineering & manufacturing solutions, Enterprise resource planning, Research and development outsourcing, And testing solutions. Cognizant has three key practice areas that span its business - Digital Business, Digital Operations, And Digital Systems & Technology. The company has more than 261,400 employees globally, Of which over 150,000 are in India across 10 locations with a plurality in Chennai. The other centers of the company are in Bangalore, Coimbatore, Gurgaon, Noida, Hyderabad, Kochi, Kolkata, Mangalore, Mumbai, And Pune. The company has local, Regional, And global delivery centers in the UK, Hungary, The Netherlands, Spain, China, Philippines, Canada, Brazil, Argentina, Mexico etc.

Keyword : Multinational Corporation, Cognizant, in-house technology, Business Intelligence, IT services, Consulting.

1.INTRODUCTION

Cognizant is an American multinational corporation that provides IT services, including digital, technology, consulting, and operations services. It is headquartered in Teaneck, New Jersey, United States. Cognizant is included in the NASDAQ-100 and the S&P 500 indices. It is also one of the fastest growing Fortune 500 companies. It was founded as an in-house technology unit of Dun & Bradstreet in 1994, And started serving external clients in 1996.

After a series of corporate splits and restructures of its parent companies there was an initial public offering in 1998. Following the Y2K and dot-com boom of the late 1990s, when

companies sharpened their focus on hard business parameters such as revenues and profits, the company grew by delivering critical application development and maintenance services.

Cognizant had a period of fast growth during the 2000s, becoming a Fortune 500 company in 2011. In 2015, the Fortune magazine named it as the world's fourth most admired IT services company. In 2017, Cognizant was named in Fortune's Future 50 list.

Cognizant provides information technology, information security, consulting, ITO and BPO services. These include business & technology consulting, [systems integration](#), application development & maintenance, IT infrastructure services, analytics, [business intelligence](#), [data warehousing](#), [customer relationship management](#), [supply chain management](#), engineering & manufacturing solutions, [enterprise resource planning](#), [research and development](#) outsourcing, and [testing](#) solutions.

Cognizant has three key practice areas that span its business — Digital Business, Digital Operations, and Digital Systems & Technology.

Like many other IT services firms, Cognizant follows a [global delivery model](#) based on [offshore software R&D](#) and [offshore outsourcing](#). The company has a number of [offshore development centers](#) outside the United States and near-shore centers in the U.S., Europe and South America.

In its early years, Cognizant gained business from a number of American and European companies with the help of the Dun & Bradstreet brand. The company's senior executives envisaged the firm as a provider of high-end customer services on-par with the six contemporary major [system integrators](#) ([Accenture](#), [BearingPoint](#), [Capgemini](#), [E&Y](#), [Deloitte](#) and [IBM](#)), but at lower prices.

The company has more than 261,400 employees globally, of which over 150,000 are in India across 10 locations with a plurality in [Chennai](#). The other centers of the company are in [Bangalore](#), [Coimbatore](#), [Gurgaon](#), [Noida](#), [Hyderabad](#), [Kochi](#), [Kolkata](#), [Mangalore](#), [Mumbai](#), and [Pune](#). The company has local, regional, and global delivery centers in the UK, Hungary, The Netherlands, Spain, China, Philippines, Canada, Brazil, Argentina, Mexico etc.

Cognizant is organized into several [verticals](#) and [horizontal](#) units. The vertical units focus on specific industries such as Banking & Financial Services, Insurance, Healthcare, Manufacturing and Retail. The horizontals focus on specific technologies or process areas such as Analytics, mobile computing, BPO and Testing. Both horizontal and vertical units have [business consultants](#), who together form the organization-wide Cognizant Consulting team. Cognizant is among the largest recruiters of MBAs in the industry; they are involved in [business development](#) and [business analysis](#) for IT services projects.

2.OBJECTIVES

- To know the leadership team at Cognizant.
- To analyse the services and solutions provided by the Cognizant.
- To know the Cognizant Partners and Alliances.
- To analyse the environmental strategy of Cognizant.
- To analyse the HR strategies of Cognizant.
- To find the competitors of Cognizant.
- To analyse the achievements and the growth of the company.

- To analyse the company using SWOT analysis.

3.SMART PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

1.Smart industrial equipment:

Equipment that predicts failures and triggers automated maintenance; plant floor equipment that sends alerts about unexpected changes, such as shortages and bottlenecks.

2.Smart packaging:

Product labels that convey offers, recipes, product history/condition; packaging that responds to environmental stimuli, such as temperature, oxygen, carbon dioxide levels.

3.Consumer home devices:

Thermostats, light fixtures, entertainment devices and security system that adjust to preferences, anticipate needs and send alerts; appliances that convey information such as food spoilage and maintenance needs; utilities systems that conserve energy.

4.Consumer wearables:

Fitness bands, smart watches, smart glasses, etc.

5.Other:

Beer kegs that send alerts on low levels, toothbrushes that convey information on brushing habits, sports equipment that tracks performance.

6.Smart building/ smart city product:

Energy meters that help conserve electricity and reduce costs; traffic signals that respond to traffic flow; transportation system send alerts on delays and re-routing.

4.CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS

Accenture provides Strategy, Digital, Technology and Management consulting services its client's of Fortune Global 500. Accenture solves the challenges of client's in the fields of process, marketing, staffing, technology. Accenture extend their technology and business capabilities through a powerful alliances ecosystem of market leaders. Accenture provides specialized IT skills and New IT solutions to clients.

Some of the clients of Accenture are:

- IQB Information Technologies Inc.
- Adobe Systems
- Alibaba
- Amazon Web Services(AWS)
- Apple
- Blueprint Software Systems Inc.
- BMC Software
- CA Technologies
- Callidus Software Inc.

- Cipher Cloud Inc.
- Cisco
- Click Software
- Collibra
- Copperleaf Technologies
- Drone Deploy
- EcoSys Management LLC.
- Ferranti Computer Systems NV.
- ForgeRock
- GitHub
- Google
- Guidewire Software, Inc
- Huawei Technologies
- Hyland Software
- IBM
- JDA Software Inc.
- Microfocus
- Microsoft
- NetApp, Inc.
- Nimble
- Nokia.
- Open Legacy
- Oracle
- Pegasystems
- Red Hat
- SAP
- SAS
- SOASTA
- Stibo Systems
- Tibco
- TIA Technologies
- Veeva
- Vodafone
- Xoriant Corporation.

5.SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN STRATEGY

Saving carbon by reducing travel intensity: In fiscal 2016, Accenture try to invest in virtual collaboration technology along with strategic shifts in its delivery model by increasing use of Accenture Global Delivery Network reduced air travel carbon emissions per employee by more than 10 percent from fiscal 2015. Thanks to the widespread use of collaboration technologies, continuing operational rigor in their delivery model, and an increased focus on virtual and regionalized training, they avoided more than 40,000 metric tons of CO₂, saved

more than US\$150 million in travel costs for Accenture and their clients, and improved work-life balance for their people around the world.

More efficient lighting and cooling: Accenture has identified enormous potential to make a difference in environmental sustainability by maximizing the use of new and digital technologies in its day-to-day operations. Frankfurt innovates with a smart LED hub. For example, in fiscal 2016, Accenture installed a cutting-edge lighting system in their Campus Kronberg office in Frankfurt, Germany. The lighting system occupies six floors, uses custom-manufactured LED ceiling-suspended luminaires, and is powered and controlled using Power over Ethernet (PoE). This eliminated the need for a traditional wiring installation and instead uses plug-and-play Ethernet cabling to power, control and relay information to the system's controllers. Adding sensors to the system turned it into a smart LED hub where each luminaire collects information on ambient lighting, humidity, temperature and occupancy, and communicates it back to the central hub. Its flexible automated control also has eliminated the need for light switches. The system switches on and adjusts the lighting if someone occupies a space, and does the reverse when they leave. Core hour and set-back programs ensure that the system operates at its most-efficient levels, and the daylight harvesting capability built into all the luminaires makes the most of daylight hours by adjusting intensity. The combined effect of LED, PoE and smart hub technology has helped reduce carbon emissions and increased energy efficiency.

6.HR HIRING AND TRAINING STRATEGY

Accenture collaborates with their clients to set up integrated programs in place to:

- **To create HR Strategy** that is nearly integrated with both business strategy and human strategy to support business results while delivering high value talent and HR services that gives improved employee and manager experience
- .Design and execute an HR working model fit for conveying ability and HR benefits proficiently and adequately on a worldwide scale to help the basic needs of the business.
- Drive driving practices and operational greatness crosswise over ability and HR forms by adjusting those procedures to the HR working model and the hidden HR innovation design.

A coordinated HR methodology, a worldwide HR working model, and steady procedures can change

HR into a finely tuned and deft association equipped for driving new levels of business esteem.

Accenture is a pioneer and thought pioneer in the HR space. The wide-achieving research activity,

"The Future of HR," has distinguished a few key attributes the HR work must create to enhance its

effect on the business:

- Find intermediary new wellsprings of ability.
- Assemble a versatile and engaged culture.
- Apply science and actuality based investigation.
- Build up a learning association.
- Reclassify employments and profession ways to encourage inner and outer labourer versatility.

At last, Accenture can enhance their customer's HR capacities and their capacity to convey

unsurprising, great HR administrations and at the same Accenture causes the HR associations to improve as a key cooperate with the business.

9. COMPETITORS

IBM: The International Business Machines Corporation (IBM) is an American multinational innovation technology-based company headquartered in Armonk, New York, United States, with

its branches spread in more than 170 nations. The organization started in 1911 as the Computing-

Tabulating-Recording Company (CTR) and was renamed "Worldwide Business Machines" in 1924. IBM produces and markets PC equipment, middleware, and programming, and gives facilitating and Consulting or consultation administrations in regions going from centralized server PCs to nanotechnology. Accenture is principally a frameworks combination, Consulting and outsourcing organization. IBM Services gives a substantially more extensive scope of administrations. That is, the examination isn't exactly one type to its logical counterpart. In any case, Accenture is the nearest "peer" to IBM's Services business.

Capgemini Consulting: Capgemini is a French multinational expert administration and business

Consulting company headquartered in Paris, France. Capgemini gives IT benefits and is one of the world's biggest IT consulting, outsourcing and proficient administrations organizations with more than 200,000 representatives in more than 40 countries, of whom almost 100,000 are in India. It was established in 1967 by Serge Kampf in Grenoble, France.

Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited: Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited regularly alluded or called to as Deloitte, is a UK-joined or incorporated multinational expert organization or firm. Deloitte is one of the "Huge Four" bookkeeping associations and the biggest expert administrations arrange on the planet by income and number of professionals. Deloitte gives a review, impose, Consulting, venture chance and monetary warning administrations with in excess of 263,900 experts all around.

11. SWOT ANALYSIS

The Accenture can be analyzed using Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Challenges by

considering different aspects [20-34].

Strengths in the SWOT analysis of Accenture:

- World's biggest consulting organization: as far as revenue it's the world's largest Consulting company which has IT and business consultancy. It has business morals and uncompromising benchmarks for managers.
- Strong Clientele: It has a large customer base with some first-class companies having Accenture as their specialists. About 90 out of the fortune top 100 companies and in excess of seventy-five percent of fortune worldwide 500 organizations have Accenture as a consulting company.

- **Service Delivery Network:** Accenture has worldwide company conveyance coordinate with presence in excess of 200 urban communities, 56 nations and utilizing 390,000 enthusiastic representatives ceaselessly attempting to give ideal administration conveyance to end clients.
- **Client-Driven procedures:** The strong business relations and customer-driven approach initiated and maintained by Accenture causes them in making industry based, supportable incentive for their Consulting accomplices.
- **Continuous change:** Like Kaizen of Toyota, Accenture is continually looking towards enhancing its abilities, contracting better and more capable labour, accordingly coordinating their guarantee